

Efficient hydrodeoxygenation of used cooking oil using molybdenum phosphide on silica supports for sustainable green fuel production

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the catalytic hydrotreatment of triglycerides using molybdenum phosphide (MoP) supported on different silica-based materials and evaluated their performance in hydrodeoxygenation (HDO) reactions. The catalysts were synthesized using the phosphite method and characterized using techniques such as X-ray diffraction (XRD), nitrogen adsorption–desorption isotherms, temperature-programmed desorption (NH₃-TPD), transmission electron microscopy (TEM), and Raman spectroscopy. Catalytic activity tests were conducted using methyl laurate (ML) and glyceryl trioleate (GLY) as model compounds, as well as used cooking oil (UCO). This study examined the effect of different supports, including silica and silica-alumina with varying pellet morphologies (cylinder and trilobe), on the catalytic performance. The results showed that MoP supported on trilobe silica (MoP/SiO₂-t) exhibited the highest conversion rates, selectivity for hydrocarbons, and long-term stability over 100 h. The catalyst demonstrated superior deoxygenation efficiency, effectively reducing oxygenated intermediates. Compared with glyceryl trioleate, used cooking oil resulted in greater conversion due to the presence of additional reactive compounds. These findings highlight MoP/SiO₂-t as a viable catalyst for scaling up sustainable biofuel production.

1. Introduction

Climate change is an undeniable reality, and atmospheric CO₂ levels are increasing annually, primarily due to fossil fuel combustion. Consequently, reducing these emissions is important. While renewable energy sources are the leading alternative, the transition toward such technologies requires the exploration of additional energy-generation methods that maintain a carbon-neutral cycle and meet Europe's decarbonization goals [1]. Europe aims to reduce CO₂ emissions by 75 % in both road and rail transport by 2050. Furthermore, EU regulations stipulate that sustainable aviation fuels must account for at least 70 % of the supply by 2050, whereas maritime transport is expected to reduce its annual average carbon intensity by 80 % compared with 2020 levels [2].

Several technologies utilize biomass waste to produce energy, such as the production of fatty acid methyl esters (FAME) via catalytic transesterification and triglyceride hydroprocessing. Compared with diesel derived from crude oil, biodiesel produced by transesterification often has a greater cloud point, greater viscosity, lower chemical and thermal stability, and reduced energy density [3–5]. In contrast,

triglyceride hydrotreatment yields green diesel with a greater cetane number, improved cold-weather performance, and greater energy density, without generating byproducts such as glycerol that require further treatment [1,6–11]. Hydroprocessing of vegetable oil (HVO) is especially promising for heavy transport sectors—agriculture, maritime, and aviation—in which electrification or hydrogen propulsion is challenging [11]. A key advantage of HVO is that the fuel can be integrated into existing infrastructure for transport, storage, and distribution. Moreover, its use is carbon neutral, as the CO₂ emitted during combustion is balanced by that absorbed during biomass growth [1,2,12], and it also reduces NO_x emissions [13] while promoting a circular economy. The consumption of hydrogen is moderate in this reaction because the used vegetable oils have low oxygen content (> 13%). The higher GHG emissions saving is produced when the residues of vegetable oils are employed, as used cooking oil, at this case, independently of the hydrogen origin, the use of used cooking hydrotreated fuel yields CO₂ emissions reductions from 80% for grey hydrogen (present technology) to more than 90% for green hydrogen (DIRECTIVE (EU) 2018/2001).

The HVO process consists of two main steps: deoxygenation and

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Fig. 1. Diffractograms of the 15MoP/SiO₂ and 15MoP/Al₂O₃-SiO₂ pellets with a cylindrical morphology and 15MoP/SiO₂-t pellets with a trilobed morphology.

isomerization. In the first step, oxygen is removed from the double bonds of triglycerides or carboxylic esters at the metal sites of the catalyst, yielding a mixture of linear hydrocarbons. The subsequent isomerization step enhances fuel properties by increasing the cetane number and

Fig. 2. Nitrogen adsorption–desorption isotherms of the prepared samples.

improving cold flow characteristics [5,9,14]. Both reactions are typically carried out under H₂ pressure to increase catalyst performance and prevent deactivation [1,7]. The literature reports three deoxygenation pathways [15–17]: hydrodeoxygenation (HDO), which produces water and maintains the original carbon number, and decarbonylation and decarboxylation, both of which yield CO or CO₂ and reduce the carbon count by one [11]. Secondary reactions such as water gas shift and methanation are also common, with the HDO route being particularly advantageous, as it supports decarbonization by minimizing carbon-containing byproducts [1].

Bifunctional catalysts, which combine hydrogenation/dehydrogenation and acid sites for dehydration, hydrolysis, and isomerization, are most promising for hydrotreatment [18]. Although metal sulfides are widely used for deoxygenation, they require sulfidation and are susceptible to deactivation by water [1,11,12]. Noble metals (Pt, Pd, and Rh) offer high yields but are limited by cost and availability [1,2,10,13,19]. Transition metals such as iron, cobalt, and nickel (or their bimetallic forms) are attractive alternatives because they are less expensive while still effectively removing oxygen from organic compounds; however, transition metal catalysts tend to deactivate rapidly [1,4,10,20]. An interesting alternative is the use of transition metal phosphides, which are active in deoxygenation reactions and enhance both catalyst stability and reactivity with respect to metals and sulfides, as demonstrated by our group's recent work [21]. Catalysts exhibit improved oxidation resistance and moderate acidity, owing to the presence of P–OH groups, which promote hydrogenation reactions [12]. In addition, ligand effects at the metal center can modify the electron density and facilitate hydrogen spillover [22].

Despite the large number of studies about the hydrodeoxygenation of vegetable oils, the studies with extrudate catalysts are scarce in the bibliography. This is an important lack because this kind of catalyst will be used at an industrial scale. For this reason, it is necessary to study the use of extrudate catalysts and complete the study with the feeding of actual used cooking oil makes the study of these catalysts close to an industrial application.

In this study, the role of different supports—SiO₂ and Al₂O₃-SiO₂ cylinder pellets, as well as SiO₂ trilobe pellets—for the active MoP phase in the hydrotreatment of vegetable oil waste was investigated. In addition, we studied the use of model molecules closer to actual vegetable oils, using different amounts of glyceryl trioleate in decane (from 10 to 90 wt%). Finally, the best catalysts were tested in reactions using real used cooking oil (UCO),.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

Catalysts were synthesized from commercially available materials without any prior purification. Phosphorous acid (H₃PO₃, 99%) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Product number 215112), and the molybdenum precursor, (NH₄)₆Mo₇O₂₄·4H₂O (99%), was acquired from Thermo-Fisher Scientific (Product number A13766.18). The supports were obtained from Saint Gobain-NORPRO and consisted of a 1.5 mm cylindrical pellet of Silica (SS 61138), a 1.5 mm cylindrical pellet of Silica-Alumina (SS 61155), and a 1.5 mm trilobe pellet of Silica (SS 69138). Additionally, n-decane (Product number D0011) was sourced from TCI Europe. The model compounds, methyl laurate (Product number W271500) and glyceryl trioleate (Product number T7752), were supplied by Sigma-Aldrich, while used cooking oil was provided by the Fuenlabrada City Council (Madrid, Spain); the latter was utilized as received after undergoing a simple filtration to remove suspended solids.

2.2. Synthesis

MoP catalysts supported on commercial silica were synthesized using

the phosphite method previously reported [5,12,13,21]; notably, this method eliminates the need for a calcination step [24]. The catalyst, containing 15 wt% molybdenum, was prepared via incipient wetness impregnation using $(\text{NH}_4)_6\text{Mo}_7\text{O}_{24}\cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Thermo Scientific) as the molybdenum precursor and an equimolar amount of phosphorous acid (H_3PO_3 , Merk) as the phosphorus source. The precursors were dissolved in 2 mL of water per gram of silica or silica-alumina and added dropwise to the support. The resulting mixture was dried overnight in an oven at 80 °C. Reduction was performed in a fixed-bed quartz reactor under a high hydrogen flow (1000 mL/min) at a heating rate of 3 °C/min until reaching 580 °C, where it was held for 2 h to form the desired metal phosphides without impurities. The high H_2 flow promoted the formation of small particles [25]. Finally, the catalyst was passivated at ambient temperature by exposure to a 0.5 % O_2 flow for 2 h to prevent oxidation before use.

The catalysts were labeled MoP/SiO₂ and MoP/SiO₂-Al₂O₃, which correspond to cylinder pellets, and MoP/SiO₂-t that refers to trilobe pellets.

2.3. Characterization

The catalyst properties were assessed using several techniques:

2.3.1. X-ray diffraction (XRD)

Diffraction profiles were recorded on an X'Pert Pro PANalytical diffractometer equipped with a Cu K α radiation source ($\lambda = 0.15418$ nm) and an X'Celerator detector. The ground samples were placed on a stainless-steel plate and analyzed over a 2θ range of 4° to 90° with a scanning rate of 0.02° per step and an accumulation time of 50 s. The diffractograms were processed using X'Pert HighScore Plus software. The XRD analysis was realized using passivated catalysts.

2.3.2. Textural properties

Nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms were measured at -196 °C using a Micromeritics ASAP 2420 instrument. The specific surface area was determined via the BET method (using a relative pressure range of 0.03–0.3), whereas pore size distributions were obtained from the desorption branch using the BJH model. The analysis was done using passivated catalysts.

2.3.3. Acidity

Ammonia temperature-programmed desorption (NH_3 -TPD) was conducted on a Micromeritics Autochem II 2920 apparatus with a TCD detector. Approximately 150 mg of passivated sample was first reduced under H_2 at 450 °C, cooled to room temperature, and then exposed to a 5 % NH_3 /He mixture for 30 min at 100 °C. After purging with He to remove physically adsorbed NH_3 , the sample was heated under He flow at 15 °C/min to 800 °C. The amount of the grade of acidity was calculated in function of the area, taking into account the temperature range of each grade: weak acidity (100–250 °C), moderate acidity (250–400 °C) and strong acidity (400–800 °C).

$$\text{Oxygen removed} = \frac{\text{initial oxygen content (Inlet)} - \text{final oxygen content (Outlet)}}{\text{initial oxygen content (Inlet)}} \bullet 100$$

2.3.4. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM)

The TEM analyses were carried out using a JEOL-2100F transmission electron microscope operating at 200 kV with a field emission gun (point resolution of 0.19 nm). An EDX detector (X-Max80 by Oxford Instruments) provided semiquantitative chemical analysis, and images were processed with Gatan Digital Micrograph software. The TEM

analysis was done over reduced/passivated samples.

2.3.5. Raman spectroscopy

Raman spectra were acquired using a Renishaw inVia Raman microscope under ambient conditions. The system features a 532 nm laser, a thermoelectrically cooled CCD detector, and a holographic super-Notch filter. The scattered light was dispersed via a 1200 lines/mm grating monochromator and captured by the CCD camera. The Raman analysis was realized over catalyst after reaction.

2.4. Activity

The catalytic activity for the hydrodeoxygenation of methyl laurate (ML), glyceryl trioleate (GLY), or used cooking oil (UCO) was evaluated in a trickle-bed reactor (internal diameter 17 mm) operating under parallel flow conditions to ensure effective contact among the gas, liquid, and solid phases. The MoP catalyst (3 g that corresponds to 3 cm bed length) was initially reduced in situ at 450 °C under atmospheric pressure. The reactor was then cooled to 300 °C and pressurized to 2 MPa. The reaction conditions included a hydrogen flow rate of 600 mL/min and a liquid feed rate of 0.3 mL/min for ML, GLY, or used cooking oil (UCO), as optimized in previous studies [4,5,21]. Gas-phase products were analyzed online every 30 min using an Inficon 3000 Micro-GC equipped with four channels, two 5A molecular sieves, a Porapak Q, and a Stawilwax column. Liquid products were periodically collected and analyzed offline every 2 h by both liquid chromatography (Agilent 1200 HPLC with an LC ZORBAX Eclipse Plus C18 column and a mobile phase of 85:10:5 butanol:water:isopropanol, equipped with UV detectors) and gas chromatography (Agilent 6850A GC with a DB-5MS column and a flame ionization detector). The oxygen content in the reagent and products in hydrodeoxygenation reactions was determined directly from the samples using an oxygen analyzer (rapid OXY Cube, Elementar). This equipment has a TCD detector for identifying the oxygen in each sample as CO, which is completely separated from interfering gases by a trap system. The amount of raw material was weighed (10–12 mg) and then introduced into the equipment, and the sample was pyrolyzed at 1450 °C under He flow. The detector measured the CO amount in each sample to calculate the oxygen amount content using a calibration curve.

The conversion, selectivity, and oxygen removed were calculated using the following equations:

Conversion calculation

$$\text{Conversion} = \frac{\text{initial molar flow (Inlet)} - \text{final molar flow (Outlet)}}{\text{initial molar flow (Inlet)}} \bullet 100$$

Selectivity calculation

$$\text{Selectivity} = \frac{\text{molar flow of product}_i}{\sum \text{molar flow products}} \bullet 100$$

O removed calculation

3. Results and discussion

The XRD pattern for the catalysts supported on silica shows no distinct diffraction peaks (Fig. 1), whereas the MoP/Al₂O₃-SiO₂ catalyst

Table 1
Textural properties of the catalysts and supports.

Catalyst	BET (m ² /g)	Pore volume (cm ³ /g)	Pore diameter (nm)
SiO ₂	224	0.92	12.7
Al ₂ O ₃ -SiO ₂	377	0.57	5.8
SiO ₂ -t	237	0.91	12.4
15MoP/SiO ₂	146	0.50	14.1
15MoP/Al ₂ O ₃ -SiO ₂	240	0.25	5.4
15MoP/SiO ₂ -t	167	0.53	13.5

produces peaks at 38°, 45°, and 67° corresponding to γ -Al₂O₃ (ICDD pattern 00-010-0173). This suggests that the MoP phase is either amorphous or consists of particles that are too small to be detected by XRD, regardless of whether the support is silica or silica-alumina and is independent of the pellet morphology.

Nitrogen adsorption-desorption analysis revealed a type IV isotherm with an H1 hysteresis loop, which is typical of mesoporous materials [26,27] (Fig. 2). While the isotherms for both pure silica supports are very similar, the isotherm for the catalyst prepared on silica-alumina has a lower total adsorbed volume, with a relatively greater contribution from small pores and a much smaller proportion of large pores. Table 1 summarizes the textural properties of both the supports and the corresponding catalysts. The specific surface area and pore volume clearly decrease in the catalysts compared with their supports, whereas the pore diameter remains largely unchanged. This decrease is attributed to the deposition of MoP particles within the interparticle spaces.

NH₃-TPD was used to analyze the acidity of the prepared catalysts. The ammonia desorption profiles show the presence of a main peak at low temperatures and a small contribution at higher temperatures for all samples (Fig. 3). The amounts of acid various strengths are listed in Table 2. Both catalysts prepared with silica supports (cylinders and trilobes) have similar acidity and TPD profile distributions, with a main peak at approximately 200 °C (weak acid sites) and a shoulder at higher temperatures (moderate acid sites). However, the catalyst prepared with silica-alumina has more weak acidity and less moderate acidity than was observed for the silica-based catalysts. MoP/Al₂O₃-SiO₂ produces a peak in the range of strong acid sites, which can be attributed to the alumina-silica support. The presence of moderate acidity, such as in silica-based catalysts, can promote the deoxygenation reaction [28,29].

The micrographs of the MoP/SiO₂ samples prepared on different pellets revealed the presence of small particles of MoP on the silica

Fig. 3. NH₃-TPD profiles of the 15MoP/SiO₂, 15MoP/SiO₂-t and 15MoP/Al₂O₃-SiO₂ catalysts.

Table 2
Total acidity of 15MoP/SiO₂, 15MoP/SiO₂-t and 15MoP/Al₂O₃-SiO₂.

Catalyst	Acidity		
	Weak strength (mmol/g) _{100-250 °C}	Moderate strength (mmol/g) _{250-400 °C}	Strong strength (mmol/g) _{400-750 °C}
MoP/SiO ₂	0.12	0.09	0.01
MoP/SiO ₂ -Al ₂ O ₃	0.14	0.04	0.08
MoP/SiO ₂ -t	0.12	0.08	0.01

support (< 2 nm) (Fig. 4). However, some differences are observed between the samples prepared with different pellets. The particle size distribution allows us to calculate the particle size of the samples (see supplementary information, Figure S1). MoP particles of the sample prepared with the trilobe pellet support are slightly smaller (\approx 1.1 nm) than those of its cylindrical pellet support (\approx 1.8 nm).

The performance of the catalysts was evaluated in the hydrodeoxygenation (HDO) of a model compound, methyl laurate (ML). The investigation focused on the influence of different support materials—silica versus silica-alumina with cylindrical morphology—on catalytic performance. Fig. 5 shows the reaction profiles of the catalysts. The MoP/SiO₂ catalyst exhibited an induction period during which the conversion increased until reaching a steady state at approximately 6 h of time-on-stream (TOS), after which the conversion remained constant. In contrast, the conversion of the MoP/Al₂O₃-SiO₂ catalyst continuously decreased with increasing TOS, suggesting gradual deactivation. At 24 h TOS, the MoP/SiO₂ catalyst achieved a conversion of approximately 81 %, whereas the MoP/Al₂O₃-SiO₂ catalyst only reached approximately 72 %.

A similar trend was observed in the selectivity for C₁₂+C₁₁ hydrocarbons. The MoP/SiO₂ catalyst not only attained higher selectivity values across all TOSs but also stabilized at a lower TOS than its MoP/Al₂O₃-SiO₂ counterpart, which exhibited a slight decrease in selectivity at lower TOSs before stabilizing at extended time on stream. At 24 h TOS, the selectivity of the MoP/SiO₂ catalyst was approximately 93 %, whereas the MoP/Al₂O₃-SiO₂ catalyst showed a selectivity of only 81 %.

These differences in performance can be explained by the distinct physicochemical properties of the supports. The MoP/Al₂O₃-SiO₂ catalyst possesses strong acid sites (as evidenced in Fig. 3 and Table 2), which are lesser extent in the MoP/SiO₂ sample. The presence of these strong acid sites may facilitate secondary reactions, thereby contributing to the observed deactivation [29]. Conversely, the higher proportion of moderate acid sites in the MoP/SiO₂ catalyst appears to favor the HDO reaction [28,29]. These findings highlight the critical role of support acidity in the rational design of catalysts for hydrodeoxygenation reactions [29–31].

We then investigated the effect of pellet morphology on the reaction yield by comparing cylindrical and trilobe silica pellets in the 10GLY/C₁₀ reaction (Fig. 6), as these morphological variations may influence the distribution of MoP. The high performance of the catalyst with the model compound methyl laurate (ML) prompted the study of its performance with glyceryl trioleate (GLY) diluted in n-decane (C₁₀), a formulation that more closely resembles actual vegetable oils. Dilution in n-decane was used to mitigate operational issues associated with the high viscosity of GLY, such as pumping difficulties and potential blockages in the reactor pipelines. The catalysts comprising MoP supported on either cylindrical or trilobe silica exhibited similar overall catalytic behavior, with no significant differences in activity observed. Nevertheless, the MoP/SiO₂ catalyst prepared using trilobe pellets demonstrated increased stability and selectivity. This improved performance could be attributed either to the superior dispersion of metal phosphide particles, as evidenced by TEM analysis due to homogeneity and lower particle size (Figure S1), or to the enhanced fluid dynamic

Fig. 4. TEM micrographs of MoP/SiO₂ (top) and MoP/SiO₂-t (bottom).

Fig. 5. Catalytic activity results for HDO of ML with the MoP/Al₂O₃-SiO₂ and MoP/SiO₂ catalysts, both of which are supports with a cylindrical morphology and 24 h of time on stream (TOS).

Fig. 6. Catalytic activity results of the MoP/SiO₂ and MoP/SiO₂-t catalysts in the HDO of 10 wt% GLY in n-decane after 24 h on stream.

Fig. 7. Conversion and selectivity results obtained with the MoP/SiO₂ trilobe catalyst for the x wt% GLY/C₁₀ reaction (x = 10, 20, 30, 40, 50 and 90) over 24 h.

behavior, which facilitates improved mass transfer [32,33]. Consequently, the MoP/SiO₂-t catalyst was selected for further investigation.

The chosen MoP/SiO₂-t catalyst was subsequently tested using different concentrations in n-decane. Fig. 7 summarizes the activity test results for various GLY concentrations in the feed. The results indicate that increasing the GLY concentration leads to a decrease in conversion; specifically, a feed comprising 10 wt% GLY in C₁₀ achieved a conversion of 97 % at 24 h, whereas a feed with 90 wt% GLY in C₁₀ resulted in a conversion of 78 % at the same time point.

In all cases, C₁₈ hydrocarbons were the predominant reaction products. Although the selectivity for C₁₈ hydrocarbons was high overall, selectivity decreased at lower conversion levels due to the formation of oxygenated intermediates. Notably, hydrocarbons—primarily C₁₈, with minor contributions from C₁₆ and C₁₄—were detected only when the conversion exceeded 90 %. The selectivity to hydrocarbons is high for the concentrations studied, but some changes were observed. The selectivity to hydrocarbons C₁₈ was constant up to a concentration of GLY of 40 wt%, but for higher concentrations decreases, this effect can be related with the decrease in the conversion observed for higher GLY concentrations. For lower conversion than 90 % the presence of oxygenated reaction intermediates was detected decreasing the concentration of hydrocarbons (final product).

Long-term catalytic performance was assessed in 100-hour experiments using the MoP/SiO₂ trilobe catalyst with a feed containing 10 wt % glyceryl trioleate (GLY) in decane (C₁₀). As shown in Fig. 8, the catalyst initially achieved a conversion of 98 % during the first 24 h. Thereafter, the conversion decreased gradually, reaching 95 % by the end of the 100-hour run. C₁₈ hydrocarbons were the primary product, with a selectivity of approximately 80 %, which remained constant

Fig. 9. Raman analysis of the MoP/SiO₂-t catalyst used in the 10 wt% GLY/C₁₀ reaction over 100 h after the cleaning procedure with hexane.

throughout the reaction. Minor amounts of C₁₆, C₁₂ hydrocarbons, and oxygenated compounds were also detected. These findings demonstrate the robust performance and high stability of the MoP/SiO₂-t catalyst under the tested conditions. The observed decrease in conversion is likely associated with the deposition of carbonaceous residues from secondary reactions [23,34] or the adsorption of heavy intermediates that block active sites [23,35].

Raman spectroscopy was utilized to determine the nature of the carbon deposits on the spent catalyst (Fig. 9). Before analysis, the catalyst was retrieved from the reactor, rinsed with hexane, and air-dried at RT overnight [20]. The Raman spectrum displayed two broad bands at 1368 and 1568 cm⁻¹, corresponding to the D and G bands, respectively [36], which serve as indicators of carbon deposition. The D band arises from structural defects, while the G band signifies the

Fig. 8. The long-term catalytic activity of the MoP/SiO₂ trilobe catalyst resulting from the HDO of 10 wt% GLY/C₁₀, 100 h TOS.

Fig. 10. Conversion and selectivity results obtained with the MoP/SiO₂-t catalyst for 50 wt% UCO in C₁₀ and 50 wt% GLY in C₁₀ reacted over 24 h (A) and reacted over 100 h with 50 wt% UCO in C₁₀ (B).

presence of a graphitic structure. The low intensity of both bands suggests a relatively small amount of carbon deposits, and the similar intensity of these bands further implies the presence of poorly crystalline carbon.

The outstanding performance of the MoP/SiO₂-t catalyst with both model compounds prompted us to evaluate its activity with used cooking oil (UCO) as a real waste sample. Fig. 10 illustrates the performance of the catalyst with 50 wt% UCO in C₁₀ feed as compared to a reference test sample using a 50 wt% glyceryl trioleate (GLY) solution in decane (C₁₀). Notably, the UCO feed achieved a greater conversion (92 %) than the GLY feed (82 %), likely due to the presence of additional reactive components in UCO (e.g., free fatty acids, monoglycerides, and diglycerides) that are more reactive than triglycerides. This excellent performance was maintained over the full 100 h of the experiment, with consistently high conversion and no evidence of catalyst deactivation.

Conversion was determined by monitoring the disappearance of characteristic peaks via HPLC. However, this approach does not fully capture the removal of all oxygenated intermediates, so the oxygen content in the product samples was also analyzed (Table 3). The results indicate that higher concentrations of GLY correlate with lower levels of oxygen elimination, which aligns with the observed conversion trends (Table 3 and Fig. 7). In all cases, the measured oxygen elimination was less than the conversion, suggesting the formation of partially oxygenated intermediates. This observation is consistent with the hydrocarbon selectivity data (Table 3 and Fig. 7). Similar behavior was observed with the UCO feed. Although the degree of oxygen removal was lower than the overall conversion of the primary reactants, the degree of deoxygenation achieved was greater than that observed for the GLY model compound at equivalent concentrations (Table 3).

4. Conclusions

MoP catalyst extrudate supports based on SiO₂ are effective in the hydrodeoxygenation of esters. Both silica supports outperform their silica-alumina counterpart. The silica catalyst's high conversion, selectivity, and stability can be attributed to the presence of medium-strength acid centers, which promote rapid transport of reaction intermediates to the active sites, as demonstrated by NH₃-TPD analysis. Additionally, the support's shape plays a role in catalytic performance; silica pellets with a trilobe morphology exhibit better performance than cylindrical ones. This enhancement may result from a higher dispersion of the MoP phase on the support, improved fluid dynamics leading to enhanced mass transfer, or a combination of both factors. The MoP/SiO₂ catalyst with trilobe-shaped silica (MoP/SiO₂-t) delivers promising yields in the HDO reaction using model compounds such as methyl laurate and glyceryl trioleate, as well as when processing used cooking oil as a real-world sample. This study indicates that the MoP/SiO₂-t catalyst is a strong

Table 3

Oxygen removed in the x wt% GLY/C₁₀ reaction and the x wt% UCO in C₁₀ reacted with the 15MoP/SiO₂-t catalyst.

Reaction	% O eliminated
90 wt% GLY ^a /C ₁₀ (24 h)	42.1 %
50 wt% GLY ^a /C ₁₀ (24 h)	74.2 %
50 wt% UCO ^b /C ₁₀ (24 h)	77.2 %
50 wt% UCO ^b /C ₁₀ (100 h)	77.0 %

^a GLY: glyceryl trioleate

^b UCO: Used Cooking Oil

candidate for future scale-up studies in HVO (hydrotreating waste vegetable oil) technology.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Paula Mármol: Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Diana García-Pérez:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Investigation. **Silvia Morales-de-laRosa:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Resources, Project administration, Methodology. **Jose M. Campos-Martin:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis. **Patricia Reñones:** Writing – original draft, Supervision, Investigation, Formal analysis.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.cattod.2025.115419](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cattod.2025.115419).

Data Availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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